

THE IMPORTANCE OF CONNECTION CREATING ART WORKS IN INTERDISCIPLINARY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the specific benefits of having to master other disciplines in the creation of fine art works and the work of several great artists in this regard.*

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The science of visual arts is directly related to all academic subjects. In the process of depicting a living human figure, a good knowledge of biology or in the process of writing portraits of historical figures, the culture of the period in which they lived, their unique national dress, lifestyle, in short, a deep knowledge of the history of that time is required. Many examples like this are a clear evidence of the inextricable connection between fine arts and other disciplines. In particular, the relationship is more evident in the sciences of biology, geography, labor, drawing, mathematics, physics, history, language, and literature.

This connection is made both theoretically and practically. First of all, the teacher should equip the visual arts rooms in the school with equipment and display tools that reflect the connection between these subjects.

In the cabinet, it is necessary to organize a base of the program, textbooks and exhibition materials of subjects such as labor, mathematics, drawing, geography, literature, biology, history, which are very close to visual arts.

Looking at the mosaic, we can witness that the artists of all eras not only deeply mastered many sciences, but also carried out scientific works, which points to the need for a person who creates works of art to master all sciences in depth.

Leonardo da Vinci, the founder and typical representative of the Renaissance style, tried his hand at many types of art, advanced ideas in the fields of mathematics, mechanics, and physics. For Leonardo, art became a means of knowing life. His realistic pictures served as illustrations for his scientific works. This feature, characteristic of the artist's character, determines the unique aspects of the painting he created. Each of his works is created in the essence of studying life, warmed by the warmth of the artist's soul and expressing his attitude towards life. At the end of his life, he works on scientific observations and their systematization. Begins to write a treatise on colorful imagery. Although this treatise was not completed, the collected and preserved parts showed him as a mature theoretician of realistic art. His ideas about line, color perspective, and color science have not lost their value.

It is known from history that, in addition to sculpture and painting, Michelangelo, another representative of the European Renaissance, was also involved in poetry and architecture in the last years of his life. One of the clear examples of this is his work on the architecture of St. Peter's Cathedral, Capitoline Square in Rome from 1546, which was completed after his death based on his design, and his book "Poems" was first published posthumously in 1623

About Ivan Ivanovich Shishkin, one of the great Russian painters of his time, his first wife Yevgenia Aleksandrovna says that if I. Shishkin had not become a famous artist, he could have become a botanist. Because his desire to convey life realistically in his works made him

'forced a careful study of plants. He did this both during his first trip to Europe and during his retirement (that is, at the Academy's expense) during a trip to the Czech Republic. He claims that he always had plant manuals and a microscope at hand. If we look at the lives of artists of all times, we can see that all of them perfectly mastered not only visual arts, but also other disciplines. Therefore, in creating his work plan, the art teacher should clearly indicate which subject each lesson is connected with, as well as the connection of the art subject with other subjects of different nature and content. and it is necessary to envisage implementation in forms.

This connection is made according to the purpose, task and content of the subject of the lesson. First of all, pencil drawing or painting depending on the object itself, creating a thematic composition, artistic decoration, sculpting, practical art classes are interconnected. Then these classes of visual arts are conducted in connection with such subjects as botany, zoology, mathematics, drawing, literature, geography, and labor. When drawing a still life with fruits, botanical materials must be used, when drawing birds and animals, the lesson is based on the materials of zoology, when drawing geometric shapes, the teacher should connect with mathematics and drawing science, if necessary, technical tools, and physics in the lesson when drawing a picture. science materials are used. When drawing a picture of household goods, work tools, it is connected with the science of labor. Especially in the lessons of the study of works of art, literature, history, geography, biology, physics, labor, and astronomy are referred to.

To sum up, the experiences of the advanced teachers of this subject show that in today's fast-paced world, a visual arts teacher does not widely use interdisciplinary in the process of teaching each subject to young students. cannot achieve the result and the student may encounter certain obstacles in the process of mastering the science of young people, especially elementary school students. This will have an effect on the content of their future works. In a word, the life of the created work depends not only on the skill of the author of the work, but also on how well he mastered other disciplines related to this topic.

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